

CREATING WINNING ORGANISATIONS THROUGH EFFECTIVE TEAM WORK

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Abstract:

The business world of today is changing at a fast pace. We have seen organizations reengineered, flattened, and redeployed with leadership styles and management techniques designed to produce new competencies that are very different from the traditional practices. The result of these forces is that many of the jobs have been eliminated, layers of management have been removed, and companies have repeatedly shifted strategy and focus to enhance productivity through team work.

Keywords— reengineered, leadership, productivity, strategy, team work.

INTRODUCTION:

The final decade of the 21st century has exposed us to far-reaching changes at a pace not witnessed in the past years. Organisations that dominated the industries have discovered that their leadership is challenged in ways that they never imagined. It is clear that conducting business in the old ways is not only undesirable, but next to impossible. In a competitive business environment one needs to anticipate many types of changes including shifting of customer expectation, emerging technological development, evolving regulatory requirements and societal expectations, strategic shifts in the thrust made by competitors. Since no one has the time or resources to reinvent solutions.

Organisations now set benchmarks for new ideas, new insights and best practice to give them the competitive edge. To create their own successful future, they must learn from their environment, from the best and brightest competitors in the industry. Competition has taken new dimensions and Indian companies are required to compete globally. Our tried and tested knowledge gained from operating in regulated and controlled environment no more holds good. There is a realisation that we can no more continue to manage business in future as it was done in the past.

People at all organizational levels have been called on to take new initiatives and are required to make additions to their responsibilities. It seems that everywhere you turn there is a new claim being made about the importance of teams and the need to organize business around them. There are TQM teams, self-managing teams, project teams, interdepartmental teams, web teams, design teams, councils, boards, and with the help of technology, e-teams. As customers become more sophisticated and economic and competitive pressures increase, companies around the world are confronted with the same dilemma: how do we create and lead more effective teams?

In response to this new-pressing demand, a new area of research for the organisation has opened up of how to build and manage effective teams in organisation. Teams are created when a leader declares a mission, and the need for a team to fulfil that mission. Team is a commitment-based phenomenon and leadership is a learned competence, not an aspect of character.

THE REALM OF TEAMS--

There are three essential types of social organization -- teams, communities, and families. Three fundamental variables distinguish each type of organization

- The horizon of over which non performance and non conformance are tolerated.
- The set of commitments that constitutes each one of them.
- The role of leadership.

The Horizon of Time

Perhaps the most important variable in distinguishing teams from communities and families is the horizon of time over which non performance and non conformance are tolerated. In an authentic team, this horizon is very short. If we look to the simple yet classic example of sports, we can see that those players who do not perform are either quickly retrained or replaced. The same is true of non conformance. A successful coach knows that a player with an ongoing bad attitude must be removed before he brings down the morale of the entire team and undermines the authority of the coach.

In a community, the horizon of time is much longer. Depending on the nature of the community (which could be anything from a social club to a nation), non performance and non conformance are tolerated for years .Yet at the same time there are guidelines, rules, and laws, which if violated will eventually be a cause for sanctions.

In a family, the horizon of time is infinite. There may be all sorts of violations of family norms or even declarations of separation, but this does not change the fact that family members retain that status forever.

It is important to understand the difference among these three types of organization. Lack of clarity about the differences is the source of many of the many breakdowns in organisation.

Team is a commitment-based phenomenon--

A team is a commitment-based phenomenon where each member of the teams holds a specific set of commitments with and to the other members. It is the willingness to make and live by these commitments that separates them from their competitors. In other words a commitment is what constitutes a team. Simply stated, teams cannot remain teams and succeed in the projects they undertake unless people on the team make these commitments and take the actions that are consistent with them.

The role of leadership--

The leaders hold an important position for the team. Gone are the days when leaders were considered to be borne .Nowadays leaders are being created. They are the pivots around which the whole team members work and look for support for increasing organisational productivity.

FACETS OF TEAM WORK--

There are six facets of teams which describe the quality of teamwork. These six facets are—

Communication—It is a means for the exchange of information among members. For effective communication there should be openness with information sharing among team members.

Coordination--One important component of the quality of collaboration in teams is the harmonization and synchronization of these individual contributions. There needs to be an agreement on schedules, budgets with proper co-ordination among all.

Balance of Member Contributions--It is important that every team member is able to contribute all task-relevant knowledge and experience to the team, as it is considered essential for teamwork quality. Tasks should be balanced with respect to each member's specific knowledge and experience.

Mutual Support--Intensive collaboration of individuals depends upon a cooperative rather than a competitive frame of mind as mutual support is more productive than are the forces of competition.

Effort--Team norms regarding the effort of team members are of equal importance to the collaborative team process, which is visible in the form of sharing of workload and deciding priorities of the team's with high level of effort by all team members.

Cohesion—It is the degree to which team members desire to be the member of the team and contribute to group goals.

SOME TYPES OF TEAMS--

Functional teams--They are formed by members of the same department who share responsibilities with other members along with their supervisor who designate responsibilities to each member.

Cross-functional teams-- The members of such teams come from different departments for jobs and projects that require different expertise and viewpoints focussing on fast communication. Leaders typically delegate responsibilities to members depending on their individual skill set.

Self managed teams –These are self motivated autonomous teams, who share both leadership and responsibilities jointly. Start-up companies and small businesses often use self-managed teams.

Trouble shooting teams--When issues arise within an organization, troubleshooting teams find solutions for those issues requiring complex analysis for removing obstacles and giving recommendations for improvement.

Project teams-- Project teams comprises of people from different departments who work on specific projects for their employers.
Task force teams--Organizations need task force teams when emergencies arise. These teams consists of the most efficient employees within an organization in which employees are given tasks to work upon, in order to complete projects quickly and on time.

PHASES OF TEAM WORK—

Training or forming phase--The training phase, also called the forming phase, is the initial phase of building teams and is the phase where co-workers meet. This is the stage when employees join the organisation for the first time. The team doesn't yet have established roles and responsibilities, and employees tend to feel more motivated.

Storming phase--The storming phase is one where conflict arises when employees exhibit different views which contradict with each other. There may be a disagreement regarding goals, strategy, and responsibilities in this phase.

Normalisation phase--In the normalization phase, employees form implicit rules about the group and learn how to communicate effectively while staying within their limits, with the support of group leaders. Employees in the normalization phase experience more workplace comfort and provide co-workers with constructive feedback to improve the team work.

Performance Phase-- In this phase, team members have clearly established rules and boundaries that allow them to work cohesively for giving the desired performance. Employees are highly motivated to work which is visible in the form of increased productivity.

Dissolution or adjourning phase--, also called the adjourning phase, in this phase, the project is nearly complete so employees have less workload, and supervisors complete all reports and final documentation.

HOW TO EMPOWER TEAMS TO BE MORE PRODUCTIVE—

Give your team members ownership--give authority to team members to make their own decisions and create accountability for their work. This induces a sense of responsibility regarding their work.

Ensure proper communication--Ensure effective communication within the organization as miscommunication can lead to huge reduction in productivity.

Identify your team's strengths and weaknesses--It is the duty of a manager to discover their teammates' talents and skills and keep them in mind while allocating tasks.

Team building activities--Inform and discuss with team members, their strengths and weaknesses in order to create a healthy work environment for work enhancing their productivity.

Use a project management tool--Use online project management software plays in boosting teamwork and productivity and increased collaboration between the team members. For instance, ProofHub is one such online project management software that brings the team members together.

Wholesome work environment--The work environment and infrastructure are essential contributors to improving team efficiency and productivity, as the physical environment dramatically affects how employees feel, think and perform at the workplace.

Reward your employees-- Give monetary rewards along with proper adequate and timely incentives for achieving targets to keep employees motivated to maintain their productivity levels.

Give them room to work--Give an environment to employees, where they are allowed to work together with trust and confidence in each other.

Praise a job well done--While for different employees, different things work in boosting their productivity and efficiency at work. But the employer should always give public recognition and appreciation to promote a healthy work culture in the organization. 80% of employees say they would work harder for an appreciative boss.

Clarify each person's role --As a team leader bring clarity to each person's role and responsibilities, it eliminate confusion and helps assigning the right task to the right person.

Make the daily workflow more efficient -- Try to remove workplace distractions, communication loopholes, lack of information sharing attitude, unorganized team structure to make the daily workflow more efficient.

Lead with gratitude--Practice gratitude and be thankful towards the employees at work to enhance team performance. This improves interaction and collaboration by creating a sense of belonging among employees.

Providing coaching and training--Training and skill development program along with providing feedback can improve team performance and employee retention rate.

Let employees take a break--Give regular short breaks to employees to improve team productivity and prevent burnout situation in the organization.

Provide help if needed--encourage your team members to maintain stability at work and develop confidence in them by taking the initiative to extend help whenever needed.

Minimize interruptions--Frequent interruptions can reduce productivity level so one should avoid it.

Focus on one task at a time --Focus on a single task at a time. It can lower stress levels and enhance performance of employees.

Give constructive feedback--Last but the most important on the list is to introduce a feedback process in a team. There is no hope of boosting employee efficiency if they don't know they are being inefficient in the first place. That is why performance reviews and constructive feedback are essential in increasing team productivity.

CONCLUSION--

The ability to lead and manage teams is not a quality with which people are born with and others are not. Instead, it is a competence that can be learned by anyone. Getting employees to deliver more than they thought themselves capable of, creates a winning culture that eventually goes into the making of a winning organisation with the ability to bond with a team providing proper work culture, creating an identification and passion to make everybody perform beyond their potential. Companies have taken initiative to build some core competencies and differentiate themselves to increase productivity and the quality levels. There is no single way to make the teams more productive, rather than it is situational with continuous support, encouragement and regular feedback.

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